

Paper Review of “Numb Regulates Somatic Cell Lineage Commitment During Early Gonadogenesis”

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I. Paper Abstract

Lin et al. (2017) questioned whether the asymmetry of Numb distribution in mesodermally-derived coelomic epithelium (CE) cells is a necessary regulatory step in the process by which CE cells commit to becoming supporting and interstitial cells such as Sertoli and granulosa cells which are essential to the function of the XX and XY gonads. The study was conducted following published evidence that Notch and Numb (the canonical function of which is Notch inhibition) are both present during the process of early gonadogenesis, Notch plays a role in the maintenance and formation of Leydig cells, and that the differentiation of CE cells is controlled by an asymmetry between CE cell progeny (Lin et al., 2017). In order to support this hypothesis, both wild type mouse embryos and mouse embryos with a deletion of Numb on a *Numb^l* mutant background using Tamoxifen-induced ROSA-CreER recombination were studied (Lin et al., 2017). The Lin et al. (2017) paper was the first one to confirm that Numb plays a regulatory role in embryonic gonadal development (Stevant & Nef, 2019).

II. Evidence Supporting the Major Findings

To prove that Numb plays a role in CE cell differentiation, Lin et al. (2017) utilised several biochemical assays. Firstly, wild type embryos were analysed. It was found using immunofluorescence that NOTCH2 is expressed throughout the cell and that

Numb is localised in the basolateral domain of CE cells. The use of transgenic CBF:H2B-Venus Notch reporter mice determined which cells in the embryo has active Notch signalling. It was observed that even though Notch was globally expressed in CE cells, it was only active in those with low or basolaterally localised NUMB expression.

The Numb/Numbl mutant embryo was then analysed. The Numb/Numbl mutant embryo had visible morphological abnormalities such as a rough appearance. Moreover, immunofluorescence utilising antibodies specific to gonadal cell markers (i.e. PECAM1, NR5A1, VCAM1) only labelled a few gonadal cells in the Numb/Numbl mutant embryo. This was further supported when staining for LHX9, a marker of undifferentiated fate. In the wild type embryo, only CE cells were stained. In contrast, in the mutant embryo, LHX9 stained many cells indicating that there were many more undifferentiated cells in the mutant embryo. In addition, MitoTracker staining of mutant embryos as compared to wild type embryos showed that LHX9 positive cell patches in Numb/Numbl mutants originated from CE cells as compared to a global de-differentiation event. Furthermore, qPCR demonstrated that three genes activated by Notch, namely *Hes1*, *Hes5* and *Hey1* are upregulated in mutants as compared to controls. Lastly, it was shown that blocking Notch signalling through DAPT showed a global decrease in LHX-9 positive cells. In sum, there is evidence that CE cells differentiate into supporting and interstitial cell lineages via asymmetry.

The lack of CE cell differentiation in mutant cells was also further proven when LHX9, GATA4, and SRY antibody staining of mutant embryos was used to determine Sertoli cell population size and showed a 60% reduction in the Sertoli cell population. Furthermore, immunofluorescence of mutant embryos demonstrated that Leydig cells were drastically reduced by 90% in the XY mutant gonad and that granulosa cells were reduced by 50% in the XX mutant gonad.

Some experiments did not contribute as much or at all to the evidence supporting the hypothesis that Numb regulates CE cell supporting cell lineage commitment. For instance, KI67 antibody, a marker of cell cycle activity, marked all CE cells in the mutant. However, LHX9 positive patches were not marked by KI67. This anomaly was compounded by no phosphohistone H3 (pHH3), an M phase marker, co-localising with LHX9. There was no attempt in the research paper to explain this anomaly. It was also found that Numb/Numbl mutants do not have laminin and ITGB1 localised in the basolateral domain of the cell surface. This supports the notion that loss of Numb expression leads to loss of apico-basal polarity. It was not made clear how the loss of apico-basal polarity contributes to improving the ability of CE cells to commit to the supporting and interstitial cell lineages.

A few issues regarding the findings will be raised. Firstly, Fig. 1 C' and D' show that NUMB is also present in the apical domain of some of the CE cells. This brings into question the validity of the claim that NUMB is localised in the basolateral domain of CE cells. Secondly, in Fig. 1 E' and F' it is unclear whether *CBF:H2B Venus* is only

being expressed where Numb has low expression. Perhaps an outline around the cells in the image would make visualising the stated observation easier. However, it appears that *CBF:H2B Venus* was still expressed in areas with high Numb expression. This counters the hypothesis that CE cell differentiation is controlled by asymmetry because it appears that there can be active Notch signalling in the presence of Numb. In addition, certain nuances in the results were pointed out but were not engaged. For instance, there was no proposed explanation as to why wild type CE cells had varying levels of Numb expression and why DAPT had variable effects on the mutant embryo.

The study conducted by Lin et al. (2017) provides evidence that CE cell commitment to the supporting cell lineage is a cell-autonomous event and compounds a much broader research area studying the exact mechanisms of gonadal development and sex determination (Stevant & Nef, 2019). While studies on the role of Numb in embryonic gonadal development have not been published before, it adds on to the growing list of transcription factors governing embryonic gonadal development and differentiation (Stevant & Nef, 2019).

III. Further Investigations in this Field of Research

A curious finding of Lin et al. (2017) is the loss of germ cells in mutant embryos. This poses the question of whether Numb participates in other pathways that lead to germ cell survival and proliferation. There is evidence, gathered by analysing a spermatogonial stem cell (SSC) specific Numb knockout, that SSC viability in culture is directly proportional to the level of Numb expression (Grisanti et al.,

2009). Moreover, Nishimura and Kaibuchi (2007) demonstrate that Numb regulates the internalisation of integrins for cell migration; Lin et al. (2017) state that the observed loss of germ cells is most likely due to a failure of germ cell migration. To compound the evidence in these studies, scRNA analysis comparing the SSCs in the SSC-specific Numb knockout mouse used by Grisanti et al. (2009) to the wild type could elucidate Numb cell signalling pathways in SSCs that function in viability and migration.

Single-cell RNA analyses can clarify the sequence of events that lead to embryonic gonadal differentiation by analysing the transcriptome of a single cell over relevant time points during embryonic gonadal development (Nef & Wilhelm, 2018). scRNA analysis avoids the pitfalls of classical transcriptomics by ensuring that the data observed is exclusively from a single cell and thus is not confounded by the processes occurring in other cell populations; this is particularly useful considering that the developing embryo comprises several differentiating cell populations operating in asynchrony (Stevant & Nef, 2019).

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